

Mission Soil Mirror Groups: Where do we stand? Report

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Mission Soil Mirror Groups: where do we stand? Report

1. Summary

This document is a report produced to share the main results of the work done in PREPSOIL to identify existing mirror groups and collect information on how they work. This is related to PREPSOIL objective to foster the establishment and development of Mission Soil Mirror Groups in Europe.

This document is primarily targeting the European Commission, and more specifically the Mission secretariat to support its efforts of monitoring and fostering the development of Mirror Groups across Europe, as well as representatives from national authorities that could be involved in the establishment or development of such a group in their country, in particular national delegations participating in the subgroup of the Strategic configuration of the Horizon Europe Programme Committee on the Mission 'A Soil Deal for Europe'.

The document could also be of interest to ongoing and future Mission Soil projects, as these Mirror Groups can be relevant interfaces to engage with national stakeholders.

This report presents the approach used to collect data on existing Mirror Groups, as well as the overview of existing Mirror Groups built from these data. It also shares the conclusions and recommendations that can be drawn from this overview, to support further efforts toward Mirror Group development and management.

Among these recommendations are the need to clarify at the European level the communication about such multi-stakeholder interfaces, in particular the expectations towards such a group and the need to align on the use of two concepts (the "Soil Health National Hubs" and the "Mirror Groups"). Another key result is a common interest among country representatives to strengthen their interaction and share information and good practices on Mirror group development and management.

This work concludes PREPSOIL efforts to foster the establishment and development of Mirror Groups across Europe. Through the examples of existing mirror groups highlighted in this report as well as the insights and recommendations shared, this report should help more countries to establish Mirror Group, and give concrete material to the Mission Secretariat to continue its work of encouraging and supporting the development of such groups.

2. Context

Soil health preservation, and therefore sustainable soil management, are cross-cutting issues for several sectors, such as food production, environment, housing, mining, and many more. Consequently, while adoption of sustainable management practices by land managers is a key part of soil health preservation, a good cooperation across sector is also essential.

Cooperation across sectors imply effective interactions among different stakeholders, including policymakers and decision makers, whether at the European, national, regional or local level. These interactions are essential to help each stakeholder understand the different needs and perceptions regarding soil health challenges and priorities in each sector, as well as to share a common overview of the available knowledge and relevant initiatives.

To foster such interactions and to facilitate a two-way dialogue between the regional level, the national level and the European level, several initiatives were initiated as part of Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe funded activities.

2.1. Example from the EJP SOIL programme

One of these initiatives are the EJP SOIL National Hubs. Initiated as part of The European Joint Programme “Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils” (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/862695>, <https://ejpsoil.eu/>), these hubs are multi-stakeholder interfaces, gathering key national stakeholders able to voice the needs and views of various stakeholders affected by issues related to agricultural soils. Their roles during EJP SOIL were to “voice regional and national needs, contribute to their countries’ position towards agricultural soil management, share and exchange knowledge, and thereby contribute to and learn from the EJP SOIL programme’s outputs” (see: <https://projects.au.dk/ejpsoil/about-ejp-soil/ejp-soil-national-hubs>).

The success of these hubs, and the clear benefits for countries with active National Hubs, highlighted the interest of building similar multi-stakeholder interfaces across European countries, tailored to support the implementation of the objectives of the Mission Soil at the national level.

2.2. PREPSOIL initial objectives for the establishment of Soil Health National Hubs

At the beginning of the project in 2022, PREPSOIL’s ambition was to build on the EJP SOIL National Hub in countries where they were established, while broadening their scope to address not only agricultural but all land uses, and to foster the establishment of multistakeholder interfaces mirroring the way those hubs are working in countries without an EJP SOIL National Hub.

To support the expansion of existing hubs or the establishment of new hubs, in 2023 PREPSOIL produced dedicated guidelines with pieces of advice, example of an existing hub and options as to what a soil health national hub can be used for, depending on the needs and context in the country (O’Toole, 2023).

These guidelines defined Soil Health National Hubs as a “forum which brings together relevant stakeholders in each of the member states to discuss and deliberate on the topic of soil health. Some of key tasks of the [hubs] is to define and express a common national position towards soil management, contribute to and learn from ongoing soil research, and to ensure that national and regional soil needs are soundly reflected in the programme of activities and projects in the EU Soil Mission”.

The guidelines were shared with existing National Hubs, and are also available online: <https://prepsoil.eu/news/prepsoil-releases-new-guidelines-establish-soil-health-national-hubs>.

2.3. Mission board’s initiative and their set of recommendations for the establishment of Mission Soil Mirror Groups

Early 2023, the Mission Soil Board recommended to the Mission Secretariat the establishment of Mission Soil Mirror Groups, and produced a set of recommendations to support this effort, released in March 2024 (Mission Soil Board, 2024) and available online: <https://mission-soil-platform.ec.europa.eu/resource-library/mission-soil-boards-set-recommendations-establishment-national-mirror-groups>.

The document shares the Mission Soil Board’s view on the ideal organisation of a Mirror Group, as well as insights on the process towards the constitution of a Mirror Group.

As highlighted in these recommendations, the main tasks of these groups would be “to support and report on the Soil Mission implementation at national level and gain support for improving soil health across sectors in each Member States, in particular by enhancing national and sub-national efforts to achieve the Mission Soil objectives as defined in its implementation plan”.

2.4. Building synergies to support the development of long-lasting interfaces

While some conceptual differences could be identified, with a more formal approach and stronger ownership from ministries expected for the Mirror Groups, the Soil Health National Hubs envisioned in the initial stages of PREPSOIL, and the Mission Soil Mirror Groups defined by the Mission board, shared a strong common ground. Both initiatives were expected to gather stakeholders from different sectors of activity and diverse expertise, with the objectives of providing cross-sectional views on key soil-related topics, involving national authorities, and being an interface to contribute at the national level to the implementation of the Mission Soil objectives.

Therefore PREPSOIL, the Mission Board and the Mission Secretariat interacted to align and identify synergies that could emerge. Eventually, PREPSOIL focused on supporting the development of Mission Soil Mirror Groups, starting with building an overview of Mirror Group establishment in European Member States and Associated Countries and how they are currently operating.

2.5. Aim of the report

This short report is produced to share the main results of the work done in PREPSOIL and the conclusions and recommendations that can be drawn from this overview, to nourish the further efforts toward Mirror Group development and management. The objective is to give information and insights complementary to the guidelines that already exist, to clarify the current status of Mirror Groups in Europe as well as perspectives on their management.

3. Building an overview of Mirror Group establishment

3.1. Data collection

Data collection was carried out in two phases, to build this overview of Mirror Group establishment and management in Europe.

First, an online survey was sent in June 2024, open until July 2024, by the Mission Secretariat to the national delegations participating in the subgroup of the Strategic configuration of the Horizon Europe Programme Committee on the Mission 'A Soil Deal for Europe' (hereafter referred to as "SPC members").

The results were shared with PREPSOIL in September 2024, that started analysing the data to build a first overview and define the next steps of the work.

Based on these first results, and identifying a need to go further into details and gather more information, bilateral interactions were organised between PREPSOIL and voluntary SPC members, including for some meetings other national representatives invited to join by the SPC members (coordinator of EJP SOIL National Hubs or coordinator of the existing group, for example).

These interviews were conducted following a question framework shared in advance with the participants, to refine the data previously collected. This framework is available in Appendix 1. This work was carried out in February 2025, through short interview interactions of maximum 45-minute durations. The analysis of the results started afterwards.

3.2. Responses and results of the report

The initial online survey gathered 22 responses, covering 21 different countries. Responses were very heterogeneous, as the survey included several open questions for which respondents could provide free-text answers. In the survey, 12 countries stated that they have a Mirror Group, or a "similar group", including one country whose Mirror Group first meeting was planned for later in 2024. Here, we consider as a "similar group" or "similar organisation" a multi-stakeholder group carrying out at least part of the activities expected from a Mirror Group.

Bilateral interactions were organised for 16 countries. Among these, nine countries stated they have a group carrying out part or all activities expected from a Mirror Group, some of these groups being newly formed and still shaping their actions. Six countries stated that they were planning to establish

such group, and one country explained that there was no concrete plan so far as they were still needing some information before moving forward.

Considering both the online survey and the direct interactions, 15 countries have a Mirror Group or another organisation carrying out similar activities (Austria, Belgium, Croatia, Czechia, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Lithuania, Malta, Slovak Republic, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden).

The document will mainly focus on the data shared by countries that participated to the second phase of the data collection, the bilateral interactions in February 2025, and more specifically the 9 countries that stated they have a group carrying out some of the activities expected from a Mirror Group. The detailed overview of each of these groups is available in Appendix 2.

3.3. Overview of existing groups and their characteristics

3.3.1. Scope of the groups

3.3.1.1. Land uses addressed in the groups

Figure XX shows the different land uses covered by the scope of the existing groups. Covering a land use means that the group addresses topics that are related to this land use. Thus, these observations give insight on the main discussion topics, however, it does not represent the entire expertise available in the groups, as members of the groups may have an expertise that goes beyond the topics addressed.

Figure 1: Land uses in the scope of the existing Mirror Groups or similar organisations, based on the results from the bilateral interactions (n=9).

3.3.1.2. Categories of stakeholders involved

Figure 2 shows the different categories of stakeholders involved in the nine existing groups identified during the bilateral meetings.

In the nine countries with an already existing multi-stakeholder group, the most reported stakeholder categories (represented in more than half of the groups studied) were representatives from ministries in charge of agriculture (9), from the scientific community (9), from ministries in charge of environment (6), from funding agencies (6) and from ministries (or council) in charge of research (5).

Then it is stakeholders representing Industries (4) and representatives from education (4), which are stakeholders from primary and secondary education, vocational institute, or higher education (although this last category has usually connections with the research community). Practitioners and land managers (farmers, forest owners, urban planners) and their advisors (advisory services) as well as representatives from civil society and citizen organisations were less reported as members of a group.

The “other” category in Figure 2 includes private funders, media, supply and retails and service providers.

In addition to these stakeholders, six out of the nine groups involve Mission Board members or former Mission Board members. One group was working to involve the Mission Board member from its country at the time of the data collection.

Figure 2 also shows that the degree of diversity of stakeholders represented within a group is variable, with a group having up to thirteen categories of stakeholders represented, while another group involve three different types of stakeholders.

However, the figure only shows the different categories of stakeholders directly involved in the group, and not the number nor the specificity within each category. This can be important when considering the advisory services for instance, as it may include advisors for different stakeholders and in relation to different land uses. Likewise, the figure does not show the capacity of each member to reach other stakeholders through their network, to disseminate knowledge or engage for possible feedback on specific topics.

Figure 2 : Stakeholder categories represented in the existing mirror groups or similar organisations, based on the results from the bilateral interactions (n=9). The tags numbered from G1 to G9 represents each individual group, highlighting the diversity of the stakeholders represented within a group.

3.3.1.3. *Activities of existing groups*

Figure 3 shows the main types of activities that existing groups are carrying out. All existing groups are interface to share information and voice national needs in relation to the Mission Soil activities and its work programmes. Most of the existing groups are also mobilised to share information on the projects’ outputs and other EU initiatives, and to identify synergies between the projects funded under the Mission Soil and national initiatives.

The role of the groups as interface for policy discussions and guidance for policy makers at the national level, beyond research, is carried out in fewer groups. In the groups carrying these types of activities, the action can take different forms, from the production of policy recommendations to direct consultation by policy makers. These consultations do not necessarily involve the entire group, as it can concern the solicitation of individual members with the relevant expertise.

During the bilateral interactions, it was also highlighted that in a group where members know each other, like in Finland, with experts involved having a role of sharing scientific advice as their main occupation, these kinds of discussions tend to naturally happen.

Figure 3: Types of activities carried out by the existing Mirror Groups or similar organisations, based on the results from the bilateral interactions (n=9).

Overall, the focus of the existing groups varied between countries. Some have a stronger research focus, meaning a stronger focus on activities related to voicing research needs and sharing information on the Mission Soil activities and other EU initiatives, and to foster synergies with the national research initiatives. Other groups, while still sharing information related to the Mission Soil and EU initiatives, also focus on the link with policy makers and sharing recommendations and advice with them.

However, the distinction is not a clear-cut one, as groups with a stronger research focus can also contribute to policy discussions and advice, and at least three countries with a stronger research focus have mentioned the ambition to increase their activities in relation to policy advice.

3.3.2. Organisation and management of the groups

3.3.2.1. Coordination and structure

Among the nine countries with an existing group, seven groups were coordinated by ministries, one group was coordinated by a public agency, and one group was coordinated by an association.

Five of these countries explained that their group is organised into one or several sub-groups. The number, size and purpose of the different sub-groups vary between countries.

In Germany for example, the sub-groups of the Mirror Group are organised at three levels: ministerial level, executive agencies level (agencies that manage the research programmes of the ministries); and public research body level. The members of these sub-groups are in capacity to reach out to sectoral stakeholders within their own networks, to voice their needs and expectations in the Mirror Group.

In Finland, the Mirror Group consists of a policy group involving different ministries and the Research Council of Finland (National Contact Point), and a stakeholder group, with the other stakeholders. A secretariat is ensured by a regional authority, and the group activities are managed with the support of a core group of actors, involving ministries, the Research Council of Finland and the Finnish Mission Soil Board members.

In France, the existing group is the EJP SOIL National Hub and is organised in three main sub-groups: a steering committee with a strategic role, a secretariat ensuring the operational running of the group, and an expert committee, gathering experts with diverse and complementary expertise and field of activities. The two first sub-groups involve ministries, national agencies and key stakeholders in relation to national research and innovation on soil-related topics.

Croatia's existing group is the Croatian Society of soil science and has several thematic subgroups: (i) policy and legislation, (ii) international cooperation, (iii) professional activity and (iv) promotion and marketing. Each sub-group consists of at least seven members. In addition, the group has a supervisory board and an executive committee.

The Belgian situation is specific, as there is currently two existing groups with the EJP SOIL National Hub and the Flemish Soil Hub, a subgroup of a broader multi-stakeholder platform for agricultural and food research in Flanders. Intention in the future is to gather these two groups into one Soil Mission Mirror Group, closer to the recommendations from the Mission Board.

3.3.2.2. Number of members

All participants did not share an exact number of members. This was often related either to groups being open-ended, or that while organisations are well identified, numbers of representatives from this organisation may vary.

Overall, the size of the group varies widely, with an announced number of members ranging from approximately ten, to hundreds, depending on the groups.

Although for larger groups, a core number of actors were usually more active, with some participants being involved mainly so they can be informed of the group activities.

3.3.2.3. *Interaction with the group*

Countries with an existing group mainly interact by email correspondence. Overall, meetings are organised as needed, without a fixed frequency, although most groups are meeting between one and four times a year, the most common frequency being between two and three times a year.

The meetings are primarily in hybrid or remote format, although most of the groups are trying to meet in-person at least once a year.

3.3.3. Relationship to EJP SOIL National Hubs

Amongst the countries that had participated in EJP SOIL, all mentioned a link between the existing group and the EJP SOIL National Hubs. The connection between those groups can be of varying degrees, depending on the scope of the National Hubs as well as the national authorities' ownership of these Hubs. In most cases, the two groups seem to remain distinct and the link with the EJP SOIL National Hub is ensured with overlapping members between the groups, that contribute to sharing information and support a good articulation between the actions of the National Hub and the actions of the Mirror Group. In Sweden for instance, the National Hub and the Mirror Group have a different scope and objectives, and therefore operate almost independently, with one overlapping member facilitating the exchange of information between the groups. Nonetheless, the degree of connection between the EJP SOIL National Hubs and the existing groups reported during our interviews varied from overlapping members, as mentioned above, to countries building entirely on the EJP SOIL National Hub like in France or in Belgium, where the hub should fully integrate the future mirror groups. While the Austrian Mirror Group was not established by building on the EJP SOIL National Hub, the Hub was invited from the start to participate to the Mirror Group activities, along with other stakeholders.

A common statement was that since the soil community is relatively small, some persons would inevitably be involved in both the EJP SOIL National Hubs and the Mirror Groups.

3.3.4. Three concrete examples available online

As part of this work, PREPSOIL organised a webinar in June 2025 to present some of these results. The webinar was also the opportunity to share information on the concept of mirror group, with the presentation of the Mission Board member, Teresa Pinto-Correia, as well as to have feedback from three countries on their national initiatives: Austria, Finland and Croatia.

These three groups were chosen to share a diversity of examples as they operate differently with a distinct background and starting point.

The presentation material and the recording of the webinar are available on PREPSOIL website: <https://prepsoil.eu/events/soil-mission-mirror-groups-where-do-we-stand>.

3.3.5. Alignment with the Mission Board's recommendations

As mentioned at the beginning of this overview, the existing groups do not reflect the ideal composition or organisation described in the Mission Board's set of recommendations.

However, the groups that participated to the bilateral discussions were considering or already working on developing their national group to get closer to the recommendations. Such efforts were mainly in relation to the scope of the group, in terms of land uses addressed and involving missing stakeholders.

These considerations would raise some questions, such as the size of the groups for those who want to maintain a small group, the organisation of the activities (plenary, subgroups, other) if more land uses were addressed, and even the type of stakeholders that would be ready to get involved in such groups.

3.4. Planification of future groups

Seven countries that had no concrete plan yet, were still investigating the possibility of building a Mirror Group or were concretely planning to establish a Mirror Group or a similar organisation, participated to the bilateral meetings (Norway, Latvia, The Netherlands, Turkey, Italy, Denmark and Bulgaria). In most cases, countries started their efforts with identifying national networks and stakeholders that could be invited. Coordination of the groups was not completely defined yet. Most of the countries have identified one or several potential coordinators (ministries in majority) but discussions still needed to happen when we collected the data.

Most countries said they needed more information to be able to move forward, or to convince and motivate ministries. Discussions showed a clear interest in having more information and examples on how other countries are working to establish a new group or to expand the scope of an existing group, especially when it comes to expanding the land uses addressed by the group. Interest in having more information about what is expected of Mirror Groups was also mentioned. The difference with other initiatives already in place was not always well perceived (such as those established to elaborate the national contributions and feedback to the Horizon Europe work programmes), and several countries expressed uncertainties as to what is indispensable to be defined as a Mirror Group, and how much flexibility is possible to build on what is already in place within the country.

4. Discussion, recommendations and perspectives

4.1. Drivers and challenges

One of the key elements in establishing an efficient Mirror Group is to have the **appropriate political backing and acknowledgement**, as already highlighted in previous work (Visser et al. 2023, O'Toole, 2023, Mission Soil Board, 2024).

For instance, representatives from Finland pointed out the fact that their ministries are used to collaborating with each other, and with other stakeholders like farmers or foresters. This was a strong driver to establish a Mirror Group, as they directly acknowledge the interest of such groups, and because the system is already built to facilitate interaction and cooperation among stakeholders. In the same way, Austria explained that the Ministry for Agriculture and Forestry, Regions and Water Management has been involved from the very beginning in the actions of the Mirror Group, called the Mission Action Group, that produced an action plan for the Mission Soil implementation at the national level. There was an agreement between the Ministry of Education, Science and Research and

the Ministry aforementioned, that they would engage their people to work on the national implementation of the Soil Mission.

However, while most existing groups involve one or several ministries, the ambition and capacity of a group to contribute to policy discussions beyond research, and the extent to which the recommendations are followed by decision-makers, seems quite variable.

While at least one sectorial ministry is involved in all existing groups, and most of the groups are coordinated by one or several ministries, the representatives involved are often representatives working on the Horizon Europe dynamics, such as National Contact Points, and not necessarily representatives that will design or implement the sectorial policies. Concrete links with representatives working on sectoral policies and strategies cannot be properly assessed from the available data, as it depends on the repartition of roles and responsibilities as well as working practices within a ministry.

Nonetheless, responses and insight from several countries that participated to the data collection process tend to show that, **in several cases, the perception of the Mission Soil is more of a research and innovation programme, limiting the acknowledgement of Mirror Groups as relevant multi-stakeholder interfaces to address concrete and operational issues**, beyond research. Which, as a result, can limit the support of ministries.

Discussions with representatives involved in existing groups show that **the history of interaction among stakeholders within a country, and the existence of formal or informal networks, can foster the establishment of a Mirror Group or a similar group**. In line with the observations in the existing guidelines and recommendations, in contexts where the community of scientists or the academic and research industry is small, close connections and established networking capabilities among various bodies foster mutual support, and building on these actors rather than starting a new initiative avoid stakeholder fatigue.

Fostering and maintaining consistent engagement from stakeholders appears to be challenging in some cases, including the engagement of national authority representatives. During the data collection process, it was highlighted that benefits from participating to Mirror Groups or similar organisations, or benefits from the Mission Soil was not always clear for stakeholders. Raising awareness of stakeholders, as expected from the different projects funded under the Mission Soil, seems necessary. But feedback from countries also show that **incentives are needed to mobilise those stakeholders**.

While incentives related to funding opportunities can be quite effective, a clear objective for the Mirror Group and concrete outcomes and impact, in relation to the design of a policy for instance, is also key to maintain a good dynamic. **The absence, so far, of strong soil-related policy, such as the Soil Monitoring Law in preparation, was identified as a challenge to convince and motivate stakeholder on the long-term**.

In this context, as mentioned by the participants during the data collection process, the availability of national funding both for facilitation and implementation could also help fostering engagement, as it allows the group to undertake work beyond a basic operational level.

4.2. Mirror Group or not Mirror Group

The distinction between a Mirror Group and “a similar organisation” was not always clearly made. Although the Mission Board describes in their set of recommendations an “ideal” organisation for a Mirror Group, they acknowledged the necessity to adapt the shape of the group to the national contexts and needs. Based on our observations, although some countries are closer to these recommendations, there is no group that completely fits the characteristics described in the Mission Board’s recommendations.

Therefore, the distinction made by respondents between a Mirror Group and a similar organisation seemed to be rather related on the history and objectives of the group, rather than their composition or organisation. When these discussions related to the Mission Soil implementation naturally took place in already existing groups, addressing a diversity of soil-related topics that are not limited to the Mission Soil, countries tend to say they have a similar organisation. These groups, such as the EJP SOIL National Hubs, can involve ministries without necessarily having been initiated by them in the first place. On the other hand, countries that established a group at the initiative of the ministries, or as an answer to the Commission and Mission Board’s recommendation, with one primary purpose of discussing the Mission Soil, will rather identify their group as a Mirror Group.

In this document, we made the choice to not make the distinction between Mirror Groups or similar organisations, because we believe the main objective is the establishment and effective mobilisation of multi-stakeholder interfaces, acknowledged by ministries, as a channel to share knowledge, voice national and local needs related to sustainable soil management, and advise policymakers through the production of recommendations and direct interaction with them.

Nonetheless, it is important for future discussions related to Mirror Group to clearly align and communicate on the concepts of National Hubs and Mirror Groups.

The distinction with the EJP SOIL National Hubs can easily be made, as those Hubs were established as part of the EJP SOIL and their main expected focus was agricultural soils. Of course, many of them can be a component of a Mirror Group, especially for those that have organically evolved to address a broader scope, but the articulation is clear.

However, using together the concept of “Soil Health National Hubs”, as envisioned at the beginning of PREPSOIL, and as mentioned in the current work programme of the Mission Soil, and the concept of “Mirror Groups”, may create ambiguity for the stakeholders.

Considering that involvement and ownership by ministries of such multi-stakeholder interfaces are key for long-lasting groups, and in line with the efforts done in PREPSOIL and with the Mission Secretariat and the Mission Board to align on these initiatives, **we believe the most efficient way forward is to consider these initiatives as one.**

4.3. Towards a network of Mirror Groups?

The Mission Board's set of recommendations suggested that upon its nomination, each Mirror Group with its composition and coordinator, should be listed on the Mission Soil Platform website.

Based on the feedback received, it may prove difficult to share the composition of the groups, as some countries prefer to have open-ended groups, where the stakeholders involved may evolve relatively often. However, it should be possible, and it would be useful, that **at least one contact point is nominated for each Mirror Group**, ideally the coordinator(s), and displayed on the Mission Soil Platform website. That would greatly facilitate future interactions among Mirror Groups, and would foster a dynamic of knowledge exchange and cooperation among them.

At the EU-level, regular interactions among Mirror Group managers and facilitators would appear helpful. Respondents all highlighted their interest in exchanging about how other countries address this question of Mirror Groups and how they are managing them. While a good balance between meetings and online interactions will need to be defined, fostering a dynamic of a Mirror Group network would be beneficial for the management and the efficient running of Mirror Groups. Interaction with the Mission Board and the Mission Secretariat, as recommended by the Mission Board in their set of recommendations, could be organised through this network.

4.4. Other considerations when establishing or developing a Mirror Group

In addition to the aspects of a Mirror Group already mentioned in this report (mandate of the group, coordinators, organisation, size, link to policy makers and decision makers, existing support, etc.), other practical aspects need to be considered when establishing a Mirror Group.

One is the status of the members involved in the group. Are members involved for their own expertise? Are they representing their organisation? Responsibilities need to be clear, especially when building on an existing network. Feedback from France, for instance, where the Mirror Group will build on the existing Hub, show that even when building on well-functioning initiatives, discussions are needed to address specific evolutions to develop the Hubs into Mirror Groups closer to the recommendations of the Mission Soil Board (Poinçot, 2025).

With the same logic, it is important to clearly address and prevent possible risks of conflict of interest, especially when discussing funding opportunities and synergies with the national level. Given the expected stakeholders to be involved in a Mirror Group, it is likely that several of them are willing to participate to a project funded under the Mission Soil, or are in competition outside of the group (especially for stakeholders from the private sector) as highlighted by a respondent. National Contact Points and other country representatives involved in the Horizon Europe programme already have experience in managing the activities of a group to gather input while avoiding such situations, but it is good to clearly explain and be transparent with the rules and the scope of the Mirror Group.

The establishment and development of a Mirror Group can also raise some ethical considerations, such as balance between genders, ages, and geographical coverage. While the main criteria in the

existing initiatives seem to be the expertise and availability of the members, it is good to be transparent regarding the selection criteria as well, of course, as the management of the personal information of the group members.

4.5. Perspectives

PREPSOIL had direct interaction with several country representatives during the project, with direct dialogue, during the bilateral meetings, or through meetings with national representatives and their National Hub, aiming at fostering the establishment or development of Mirror Groups.

To expand the reach of further countries, and to share examples from several countries, PREPSOIL organised a webinar, produced this report, and ensured that the material produced (recording, presentation support, report) will remain easily available to all interested parties once the project is over, on the PREPSOIL website: <https://prepsoil.eu/events/soil-mission-mirror-groups-where-do-we-stand>.

As expressed in the PREPSOIL webinar organised in June 2025, the Mission Secretariat will continue to encourage and support the development of these groups, and we hope that this overview and the examples highlighted regarding how existing Mirror Groups operate will inspire and help other groups.

This should be helped by the current European context that could bring an important incentive, with the preparation of the Soil Monitoring Law that could be adopted by the end of the year, as establishing and developing Mirror Groups or similar organisations could be a good support to organise the transposition of the directive at the national level.

5. References

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Mission Soil Board, 2024. *Mission Soil Board’s set of recommendations for the establishment of national Mirror Groups*. Independent Expert report. 10p.

Saskia Visser, Claire Chenu, Anna Besse, Niels Halberg and Teresa Pinto Correia, 2023. *Successful stakeholder participation to address soil needs*. EJP SOIL Policy Brief. 4p.

6. Appendices

Appendix 1: Questions for the bilateral meetings with country representatives to complete the overview of the establishment of mirror groups across Europe

Administrative aspects

1. Recording: Do you agree to the meeting being recorded (for note-taking purposes only)?
 Yes ; No
2. Name of the participants to the meeting:
3. Country represented:
4. Can we use the information we collect here to communicate about the establishment of Mirror group in the different countries across Europe (in a webinar, an informative report, and communication material)? Yes; No; Other:

Collecting data for the overview

5. Do you have a soil health Mirror Group in your country, or are you planning to establish one? => *for this question, we should build on their answer on the previous survey, if there is one.*
 Yes; No, but there is a similar structure; No, but there are plans to establish one; No and there are no plans to establish one

if answer to Q5 is:

> “Yes” or “No, but there is a similar structure”: below
> “No, but there are plans to establish one”: below
> “No and there are no plans to establish one”: below

6. Depending on the previous answer:
if answer to Q5 is YES or “No but there is a similar structure”:
 - Can you tell us more about how this group is structured:
 - o Who is coordinating the group? Is there commitment to the group from high-level representatives of the Ministries involved (which ones)? Is there a secretariat supporting the coordination?
 - o How many stakeholders are involved?
 - o Which land uses are in the working scope of the group?
 Agriculture; Forestry; (post)-industrial; (peri)urban; natural; Other(s):
 - o Is it build on a previously existing stakeholder group, such as the EJP SOIL national hub (if relevant?)

- What type of stakeholders are involved? *If possible, share the number of stakeholders represented in each category.*

Advisory services – n =	Foresters and forest owners – n =	Investors and private funders – n =
Civil Society and citizen – n =	Higher education – n =	Media – n =
Farmers – n =	Industry – n =	Supply and retails – n =
Ministry of Agriculture	Ministry of Environment – n =	Ministry of Research – n =
Other ministry: ... – n =	Public funding agencies – n =	Mission Soil Board member – n =
Regional/local policy makers – n =	Primary to secondary education – n =	Researchers and scientific community – n =
Vocational institute – n =	Service providers – n =	Urban planners – n =

Other:

- Could you explain how the group is functioning?
 - Are there several subgroups (policy group, one or several stakeholder groups) with specific meetings or activities? How do they interact with each other? How often / under which circumstances the mirror group meets and interacts in plenary?
 - How often do the group members meet?
 - What are the main activities of the group?
 - Exchange of information about Mission calls and activities;
 - Exchange of information about other EU soil-related initiatives (legislation, funding opportunities, events...);
 - Monitoring, dissemination and/or discussion of Mission Soil projects results;
 - Identification and promotion of synergies between Mission Soil projects and activities and initiatives at national level;
 - Identification, discussion and promotion of synergies between national initiatives and the Mission Soil objectives (national R&I agenda, Common Agricultural Policy, environmental initiatives, etc);
 - Contribute with policy discussions;
 - Contribute with leadership, advice to policy makers;
 - Communication and stakeholders' engagement activities;
 - Other activities/free text:

- Could you elaborate what is carried out in these activities?
- If the group is not built on the EJP SOIL National Hub: is there any interaction between the mirror group and the EJP SOIL National Hub?
- If relevant: Is there any plans to develop the current group to get closer to the mission board recommendations? If so, which ones? If not, is there any reason?
- Would you need a specific support to keep operating and/or develop this group?

If relevant : any benefits from these groups?

if answer to Q5 is “there are plans to establish one”:

- How far are you in the establishment process, do you already have a timeline as to when this group would be established and launched?
- If relevant, depending on how far they are in the process:
 - Who would coordinate this group? Is there commitment from high-level representatives of any ministries in the mirror group establishment process (which ones)? Are there plans to have a secretariat supporting the coordination?
 - Will you build on an existing stakeholder group, such as the EJP SOIL national hub (if relevant)?
 - Which land uses are you planning to cover in the working scope of the group?
 Agriculture; Forestry; (post)-industrial; (peri)urban; natural; Other(s):
 - What type of stakeholders are you planning to involve?

Advisory services – n =	Foresters and forest owners – n =	Investors and private funders – n =
Civil Society and citizen – n =	Higher education – n =	Media – n =
Farmers – n =	Industry – n =	Supply and retails – n =
Ministry of Agriculture	Ministry of Environment – n =	Ministry of Research – n =
Other ministry: ... – n =	Public funding agencies – n =	Mission Soil Board member
Regional/local policy makers – n =	Primary to secondary education – n =	Researchers and scientific community – n =
Vocational institute – n =	Service providers – n =	Urban planners – n =

Other:

- What would be the main objectives of the group?
 - Exchange of information about Mission calls and activities;
 - Exchange of information about other EU soil-related initiatives (legislation, funding opportunities, events...);
 - Monitoring, dissemination and/or discussion of Mission Soil projects results;
 - Identification and promotion of synergies between Mission Soil projects and activities and initiatives at national level;
 - Identification, discussion and promotion of synergies between national initiatives and the Mission Soil objectives (national R&I agenda, Common Agricultural Policy, environmental initiatives, etc);
 - Contribute with policy discussions;
 - Contribute with leadership, advice to policy makers;
 - Communication and stakeholders' engagement activities;
 - Other/free text:
 - Would you need a specific support to establish this mirror group?
-

if answer to Q5 is NO (and no plans):

- Is there any reason as to why you don't plan to establish a mirror group? (You don't need such a group, you miss a clear methodology or dedicated means to do so, ...).
- Would you need a specific support to establish / develop a multi-stakeholder group focusing on soil health in your country?

Appendix 2: Overview of existing groups in the countries that participated to the second phase of data collection

Country	Austria	Belgium	Croatia	Czechia	Finland	France	Germany	Ireland	Sweden
Land uses covered	Agriculture, Forest, Urban, Peri-urban, Post-industrial, Natural	Agriculture, Forest	Agriculture, Forest, Natural, Post industrial, Urban, Peri Urban	Mainly Agriculture and Forest, but the other land use types are also covered in the existing structure.	Agriculture, Forest	Agriculture, Forest, Urban, Peri Urban, Post-industrial, Natural	Agriculture, Forest, Urban, Peri Urban, Post-industrial, Natural	Agriculture mainly	Agriculture, Urban
Coordination of the group	Co-chairs of the Mission Soil in Austria, representative from the Ministry of Education, Science and Research and from the Ministry for Agriculture and Forestry, Regions and Water Management.	Agriculture and Fisheries Agency (Flemish Soil Hub, with the end of EJP SOIL, the National Hub should merge with the Soil Hub).	Croatian Society of Soil Science	Different initiatives in place that contribute to the actions expected from a mirror group, including a recent group that was established by the Czech Geological Survey and the State Land Office.	Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry	Ministries in charge of Agriculture, Environment and Research and education	Ministry of Agriculture	Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine	Divided by Research Council and Ministry of Rural affairs

Country	Austria	Belgium	Croatia	Czechia	Finland	France	Germany	Ireland	Sweden
Operates with subgroups	No	Two different groups that should merge in the future (the EJP SOIL National Hub and the Flemish soil hub)	Four thematic subgroups: Policy and legislation; international cooperation; professional activity; promotion and marketing.	No subgroup	Three subgroups: a policy subgroup, a stakeholder subgroup and a core group managing the activities of the group.	Three subgroups: A steering subgroups (strategic decisions), an operational subgroup (operational management of the group activities) and an expert group.	Three subgroups at different level: the Ministerial level, the executive agencies level, the public research institutions.	No	No
Categories of stakeholders represented									
Advisory services					Yes	Yes		Yes	
Civil Society and citizen	Yes								Yes
Farmers	Yes	Yes			Yes				
Ministry of Agriculture	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Other ministry:	Yes			Yes	Yes				
Regional/local policy makers	Yes				Yes				
Vocational institute					Yes				Yes
Foresters and forest owners	Yes								
Higher education	Yes					Yes			
Industry	Yes	Yes	Yes		Yes				
Ministry of Environment	Yes	Yes		Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes		
Public funding agencies	Yes	Yes		Yes		Yes	Yes		Yes
Primary to secondary education	Yes								
Service providers						Yes			

Country	Austria	Belgium	Croatia	Czechia	Finland	France	Germany	Ireland	Sweden
Investors and private funders									Yes
Media									
Supply and retails					Yes				
Ministry of Research	Yes	Yes			Yes	Yes	Yes		
Mission Soil Board member		Yes	Yes		Yes		Yes	Yes	Yes
Researchers and scientific community	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes		Yes	Yes
Urban planners	Yes								
Others	Yes								Yes
Types of activities carried out									
Mission Soil information	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Other EU soil related initiatives information		Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Monitoring Mission Soil projects results			Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes		Yes
Synergies between Mission Soil projects and national initiatives	Yes		Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes		Yes
Synergies between national actions and Soil Mission implementation	Yes		Yes	Yes		Yes			Yes
Policy discussions			Yes			Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Leadership and policy advice			Yes			Yes	Yes	Yes	
Communication and stakeholders' engagement activities	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	

These results are based on the data collected before the end of February 2025 and the authors interpretation of those data. The above table reflect the authors understanding of the establishment of Mirror Group in Europe at the time. Countries with Mirror Group or a similar organisation that could not participate to the data collection process will not appear in the table. In addition, as several countries were planning to establish a Mirror Group, and because existing groups are dynamic initiatives, these data may not reflect the exact situation within these countries at the time of the publication.

The authors are thankful to all participants to the data collection process, including participants that shared information on their plans to build a mirror group. While data are not shown here, due to the expected evolution of their situation, their contribution was both appreciated and helpful to understand the challenges and drivers when establishing a mirror group.